

WOODFIBER-PLASTIC COMPOSITES MACHINING CHARACTERISTICS¹

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ABSTRACT³

Nowadays, double-digit growth rates for industries or products are the exception rather than the norm in the US economy. Zider⁴ estimates, that "*less than 10 percent of all U.S. economic activity occurs in segments projected to grow more than 15 percent a year over the next five years*". Woodfiber-plastic composite materials (see Picture 1) experienced growth rates well in excess of 15 percent⁵, thus making them of widespread interest to the plastic and the forest products industry. For the forest products industry, a mature industry accustomed to slow or no growth, woodfiber-plastic composites offer the opportunity to enter a high growth business with respectable margins.

Currently, woodfiber-plastic composites are mainly employed as a high-end replacement for pressure treated lumber in decking applications. However, new products are announced on a regular basis. Such products are, for example, automotive applications, railing systems, boardwalks, transportation devices, or docks⁶. Other applications that will eventually surface, we believe, are for use in furniture, cabinets, doors, and windows.

Modern technology allows producing composite parts in many shapes and sizes. Today, cutting these woodfiber-plastic composite parts to size, i.e. to length, width, and thickness, most likely is the predominant machining application. Little is known about the impact that the woodfiber-plastic materials have on the tools. With the increased variety of products being made from woodfiber-plastic composites, the need to use secondary manufacturing processes to further process these products will increase. Most research so far has focused on primary production processes needed to produce materials with specific characteristics. Only slowly are efforts emerging to investigate the material properties of woodfiber plastic composites exposed to secondary manufacturing processes.

Results from ongoing research at North Carolina State University about the characterization of woodfiber plastic composites used in secondary manufacturing applications show that these materials behave differently than solid wood when exposed to sanding and routing. Also, differences among the five products tested exist.

In particular, this study investigated the material removal rate, surface roughness, and belt life when sanding woodfiber plastic composites. It also looked at tool wear and surface roughness when cutting these products. Further research is needed to verify the results from this study and individual phenomena found need to be investigated more closely in the future.

Key words: sanding, tool wear, woodfiber plastic composites, material removal rate, and surface roughness.

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⁴ Zider, Bob. 1998. How venture capital works. Harvard Business Review (HBR). November-December 1998, pp. 131-139

⁵ Eckert, Carl H. 2000. Market opportunities for natural fibers in plastics composites. Luncheon presentation. Wood-Plastic Conference, December 5 & 6, 2000. Baltimore, MD

⁶ Morton, James. 2000. Emerging applications for wood-plastic composites. Luncheon presentation. Wood-Plastic Conference, December 5 & 6, 2000. Baltimore, MD

Sanding Introduction

This paper consists in two main parts. Abrasive machine experiment and tool wear experiment. Next, the Abrasive part of the paper is described.

In the forest products industry, smooth surfaces for semi-finished or finished products are created by coated abrasives using either hand or machine labor (5). The abrasive action of the edges of the abrasive grain leads to a smooth, regular surface (2). Sanding is one of the most crucial processes when producing wood products, since the quality of this operation is readily visible.

Carrano (2) classified sanding into [1] "*white sanding*", which refers to all sanding operations that are done on the original material, prior to applying any finishing; and [2] "*finish sanding*", which refers to all sanding operations used to improve the quality and performance of the finishing materials applied.

The goal of this research was to describe the characteristics and behavior of four different woodfiber-plastic composite materials during sanding. A series of tests was undertaken to measure the material removal rate, the roughness of the sanded surface of the test specimens and the life of the sanding belts employed.

Experimental

Measurements and Analysis: Three variables were selected to be measured, material removal rate (MRR in lb/min), material surface roughness (μin), and belt life (min). The material removal rate was determined by weighing the wood-plastic piece before and after each machining cycle. The surface roughness was measured by using a stylus-type profilometer. The belt life was determined by repeating the sanding process until the weight difference before and after a sanding cycle was no higher than 0.002 pounds for at least 3 consecutive measurements. Two repetitions of the tests were performed. The average of these two repetitions is stated here. Further statistical analysis has to be done in the future.

Materials: For the sanding experiments, we used four different, commercially available woodfiber-plastic composites for decking: FIBERON [producer: Fiber Composites Corporation, New London, NC], CHOICEDEK [producer: A.E.R.T. Inc., Springdale, AR], SMARTDECK [producer: U.S. Plastic Lumber, Boca Raton, FL], and TREX [producer: Trex Company, Winchester, VA]. A fifth product, EXCEL decking [supplier: Cox Industries, Inc., Orangeburg, SC], couldn't be tested due to its hollow core. This material, however, was tested for blade wear on the router. The decking material was purchased from local lumber yards and cut into 3"x3.75" pieces. The longitudinal axis of the material was kept as the longitudinal axis in the sanding process. For comparison, Hard Maple was sanded and analyzed identically to the woodfiber-plastic samples. The Hard Maple was sanded parallel to the grain. The material was stored in ambient conditions prior to use.

Interface Pressure: Interface pressure greatly influences the material removal rate, surface roughness, and the belt life. Work by Franz and Patronsky (4) and Hinken (6) used pressures of 0.40, 0.80, 1.20, and 1.60 psi. Steward, in 1978 (10) used pressures of 0.50, 0.75 and 1.00 psi for his research, whereas Carrano (2) found that 0.50 and 0.75 psi were the two levels appropriate for measuring the outputs desired. We selected a pressure of 0.50 psi, mainly to avoid possible plastic melting during the sanding process. The pressure was applied by means of a weight on top of the flat test specimen, such that the resulting pressure of the specimen on the belt was equal to 0.50 psi. Figure 1 illustrates this set-up.

Abrasive Mineral: Different kinds of abrasives are currently used in the industry. The major ones are aluminum oxide and silicon carbide. For this study, we employed aluminum oxide, as it is the most commonly used abrasive in the industry.

Grit Size: We selected a grit size of P100, based on experiences with wood. This decision is supported by Carrano's experimental design (2), which also employed grit size P100.

Sanding Belt: 3M delivered standard 6"x48" aluminum oxide, closed coat, cloth backing sanding belts. The belts were stored in an environmentally controlled room prior to use.

Belt Sander: We used a grinder-belt sander made by Grizzly, with an abrasive belt of 6"x48" and a speed of 2500 surface feed per minute (s.f.p.m) The sander can be seen in Figure 1.

Profilometer: We used a stylus-type instrument manufactured by Mitutoyo. This instrument is widely used and is a generally accepted method of surface roughness measurement providing numerical values in agreement with current standards (1). It essentially measures the variation of the surface around an even line.

Procedure: A test procedure was developed to assure consistency. The procedure consisted of {1} identify the test piece, {2} change sanding belt and adjust belt on sander, {3} weigh test specimen and record weight, {4} fix test specimen to pressure weight, {5} sand for one minute, {6} remove dust from specimen, measure specimen weight and record it, {7} repeat {3} to {6} until weight loss of three subsequent measurements is less than 0.002 lb. If weight loss is less than 0.002 lb for three consecutive tests, measure surface roughness three times at random places perpendicular to the sanding direction.

Results

Unlike expected, these four products did not all perform similarly, but reacted individually to the sanding. The material removal rate (MRR) ranged from 0.005 lb/min on average of all intervals for the Smartdeck product to 0.012 lb/min for the ChoiceDek product. Maximum removal rate was 0.03 lb/min for the ChoiceDek product, whereas the maximum material removal rate for our control sample, the hard maple specimen, was only 0.01 lb/min. The material removal rate of the various specimens for each interval is depicted in Figure 2. Table 2 presents the individual results.

More similar results could be observed for the roughness perpendicular to the sanding direction. Smartdeck had the smoothest surface (508 μin), which was almost as smooth as the surface of our control specimen, maple (503 μin). Fiberon had, with 531 μin , the roughest surface. These results are displayed in Table 2.

Belt life varied widely. The Trex material achieved a belt lifetime of only 31 minutes whereas the Fiberon product lasted 150 minutes under the exact same circumstances. The lifetime of the belt for the hard maple control specimen was 54 minutes.

Discussion

Sanding is one of the most widely employed processes in the industry. Sanding determines the quality of the finished piece and thus has a large impact on the perceived quality of the product. Both material removal rate and surface roughness are the two main characteristics to characterize the quality of the process. Belt life, on the other hand, determines the economics of using a particular product for a specific application.

We found that the density of the individual products correlated with the material removal rates (MRR) measured to some extent. Since the density varied widely, MRR varied, too. However, further research is needed to more specifically quantify this observation. The high variability in MRR for the same material throughout a single test (as can be seen in Figure 2) may also be explained by varying density profiles throughout the material.

Surface roughness measurements differed less than the MRR or the belt life among products. However, there were measurable differences for the different products. Fiberon, with a roughness of 531 μin had the roughest surface of any of the products tested. This is despite the fact that this product appears to have a very smooth, consistent material consistency and uses very fine ground wood particles. Also, the reader needs to be aware that the differences measured were not readily apparent to the eye or to the skin of a person.

The difference in belt life was large. The performance of the Fiberon product was three to four times better than all the other specimens tested, including the hard maple specimen. Very likely, the explanation for this observation will be found in the material composition of the different products. As it appears visually, Fiberon is a very fine, smooth product with few impurities. Higher quality raw materials for the production of this product most likely are one of the reasons for the phenomenon observed.

As the sanding study showed, there are differences in regard to sanding between the four woodfiber-plastic products tested. As these products become more widely used, these differences will become more important in the selection process for users. Also, the industry that is working in the area of sanding will start looking into better, more efficient ways to achieve high quality sanded surfaces using these new composites. Of particular concern to any of them should be the problem of heat generation and dissipation during sanding in order to avoid changing the profiles and surfaces of the materials sanded.

Conclusions

Four commercially available decking woodfiber-plastic composite products were subjected to a controlled sanding experiment. The study showed that there are detectable differences among these materials in a variety of characteristics. ChoiceDek's material removal rate (MRR) was more than twice as high as the one found for Smartdeck, with Fiberon and Trex being in between. However, the roughness of the Fiberon product after sanding was higher, although only slightly, than the one of the Trex and the ChoiceDek. Belt life varied the most among products, with Fiberon achieving a belt lifetime of three to four times as long as the other products, including the control specimen.

Tool Wear Introduction

Tool life is of crucial economic importance to manufacturers of products. Not only are direct costs associated with resharpening and/or replacing tools, but the necessary interruption from changing tools stops the manufacturing process and keeps expensive equipment idle. For these reasons, producers of materials subjected to secondary manufacturing processes should be keen on selling a material that machines well and does not dull the tools more than absolutely necessary.

Whereas there are many different methods to cut materials, routing is often used to compare different materials' wear on knives. For this purpose, North Carolina State University's Wood Machining and Tooling Program (WMTPR) developed a standardized testing method to measure tool wear for wood products (9). Using this test, different materials can be compared as to their impact on knife sharpness.

Experimental

Measurements and Analysis: Blade wear was determined by measuring the nose width (NW) of the blades used. Figure 3 displays details about this measurement. After a new blade was measured (which is necessary because even a new blade has a NW of between 5 and 10 microns), wear was tracked after 31, 63, 94, and 125 feet of cutting through the material. Wear was measured at four positions along the working knife edge, the first being at the corner, then at 500, 1000, 1500 and 2000 μm from the edge that worked in the material. The Excel product, due to its hollow core, was measured at slightly different positions. The results reported are the average values from the four measurements taken every time. In addition, the surface roughness of the materials after 125 feet of cutting at three different locations on the surface cut was also measured. In particular the locations chosen were: across the cut (i.e. perpendicular to the tool movement), and lengthwise at the border and the center of the material. Three randomly placed measurements for each location were taken, and the average of these individual measurements are reported here.

Materials: The same woodfiber-plastic composite materials as reported for the sanding tests were used for tool wear. However, for these tests, the Excel product could also be tested. We only had to shift the points measured on the blade slightly due to the hollow core of the material. From each decking material, two 23.5 inches long pieces were cut. All cuts were done longitudinal along one edge and the knife cut about through two thirds of the material thickness. After 16 passes on one edge (16 passes equal 31.3 feet of cutting), the material was turned and the other edge was used for the second set of cuts. The third and fourth set of cuts (4 sets total, for a total cutting length of 125.3 feet), were done the same way on the second piece from the same material. For control purposes, we also tested a piece of white pine in the same way we did the woodfiber-plastic materials. All cuts were done longitudinal.

Blades: Exchangeable tungsten carbide knives were used for these tests. The grade was a standard 3% cobalt binder with an ultra-fine carbide grain (0.5-0.9 μm). The edge of each one was checked prior to cutting and those with a NW of more than 10 microns were rejected. The blades were mounted on a single insert tool holder by Leitz and then mounted on a hydro chuck by ETP.

Router: A Thermwood model 40 turret router with a 9 hp spindle was used for these tests. The test specimens were clamped into a special fixture. Prior to cutting with the test knives, a cut with a minimum of 1/16 of an inch depth was made along the outside of the specimen to remove potential contaminants. Table 3 shows more details of the test set-up and Figure 3 displays the routerhead and the specimen during cutting the white pine sample.

Microscope: A Keyence video optical microscope with digital picture capturing and measuring capabilities was used for measurement of the nose width.

Profilometer: The same Mitutoyo profilometer as was used for the sanding experiments was used to assess the surface roughness of the tool wear samples.

Procedure: The test procedure for the tool wear tests consisted of: {1} identify the test specimen, {2} fix specimen into specimen holder of router and fix the blade for the first cut into the blade holder, {3} reset the router program to zero position, {4} do first cut to clean the edge, then stop the router, {5} exchange blade with the appropriate one from the test series, {6} let the router do 16 passes on the edge of the specimen in the clamp, {7} remove blade and measure NW, change test specimen according to experimental plan then go to {1} until all tests are done.

Results

We found differences by a magnitude of two to three regarding tool wear for the five different woodfiber-plastic materials. Fiberon, which we found to be the material with the least impact on the tool, had an average NW of 25 μm after 125 feet of cutting. However, this is more than double the wear found in the white pine control piece (NW 10 μm after 125 feet of cutting). The other woodfiber-plastic materials did wear the blade even more than did Fiberon. ChoiceDek's NW, for example was measured with 65 microns after 125 feet of cutting, or more than twice the NW of Fiberon. Exel, Smartdeck, and Trex were with 31.5, 37.0, and 25.4 μm in-between these two materials. Table 4 displays the results of the NW after 0, 31.3, 62.6, 94.0, 125.3 feet for the six materials tested.

Wear as measured by NW differed somewhat along the same cutting edge when measured at different locations. However, no clear trend was observable. Figure 5 displays the NW of the cutting edge of the blade that was used to cut the ChoiceDek material after 0, 31.3, 62.6, 94.0, 125.3 feet of cutting. The cutting edge was measured at five positions along the blade, in particular, the points measured were at the end of the blade, i.e. at 0 μm , and at 500, 1,000, 1,500, and 2,000 μm . NW measurements after 125 feet of cutting at these points were 50, 58, 85, 70, and 65 μm , respectively.

Surface roughness did show less variability among the five specimens. Roughness across the surface cut (i.e. perpendicular to the cutting direction), ranged from 116 $\mu\text{in.}$ for the Fiberon material to 276 $\mu\text{in.}$ for the ChoiceDek material. The roughness across the surface could not be determined for the Excel product, due to its hollow core. Figure 6 shows all the individual measurements across the cutting surface for the different materials. Also shown in Figure 6 are the measurements lengthwise, at the border of the piece and at the center. Fiberon, with roughnesses of 69 $\mu\text{in.}$ at the border and 71 $\mu\text{in.}$ at the center, again had the smoothest surface. Fiberon is followed by Excel at the border (112 $\mu\text{in.}$), no measurement for Excel at the center could be taken due to the hollow core of this material. Trex was the next smoothest material, with 152 $\mu\text{in.}$ at both, the border and the center.

Discussion

As shown in the above Results section, large differences among the five woodfiber plastic composites tested in terms of tool wear characteristics were detected. The wood specimen we tested showed by far the least impact on tool sharpness of all materials used in this study. In fact, when cutting 125 feet of white pine, the NW, on average of the five points measured every time, of the knife increased only slightly from 9.0 μm to 10.4 μm (Table 4). The next benign materials, Fiberon and Trex, dulled the knife's cutting edge (NW) from 5 and 8 μm to 25.0 and 25.4 μm , respectively. The Excel and the Smartdeck material dulled the knife's nose somewhat more than Fiberon and Trex (average NWs for Excel and Smartdeck after 125 feet of cutting were found to be 31.5 and 37.0 μm , respectively), it was the ChoiceDek material that had the biggest impact on the knife. ChoiceDek wore the cutting edge (NW) of the blade from 7.0 μm prior to cutting (Figure 6) to 40.0 μm after just 31.3 feet of cuts and to 65.6 μm after 125 feet (Figure 7). This blade, although not entirely dull, would no longer be able to achieve the quality surface required in some applications. For comparison, Figure 8 shows the knife used to cut the white pine material after 125 feet of cutting.

There are several potential reasons for this higher wear of knives in woodfiber plastic composites materials. One is definitely the issue of impurities in the materials used to produce these products. This issue is of large importance to the products made from recycled plastic and recycled wood fiber. For example, Figure 9 shows a

section of the knife used for cutting the ChoiceDek material that was severely damaged from a foreign object in the material. However, even woodfiber plastic composite products made from virgin materials show more wear than does solid wood. One explanation for this phenomenon could be that the pigments used to color the composite material, which are often made from minerals, have a negative effect on blade sharpness. Other reasons such as, for example, cutting speed, knife material composition or the appropriate rake angle, could also play an important role.

The surface roughness of the woodfiber plastic composite materials was lower or similar to the one of the solid wood control sample (white pine). Fiberon had, with Rqs of 116, 69, and 71 $\mu\text{in.}$ for the measurements across the cut surface, and lengthwise at the border and in the center, respectively, the smoothest surface of all specimens tested (Table 5). ChoiceDek, on the other hand, had, with the exception of lengthwise in the center, the roughest surface with Rqs of 276, 222, and 167 $\mu\text{in.}$ across the surface, and lengthwise at the border and in the center. Smartdeck, whose surface roughness in the center was larger than the one for ChoiceDek, had values of 249, 200, and 211 $\mu\text{in.}$ for the same measurement points. In comparison, the control sample's (white pine) values for the same measurements were 180, 208, and 244 $\mu\text{in.}$ These data show that woodfiber plastic composite surfaces, in general, seem to be rather smooth after cutting. The high values of ChoiceDek are no surprise, given the large wear that this material causes on the knife. A potential source for surface roughness could be the moisture content uptake of the woodfibers freshly cut by the knife. Since these fibers are dried below the ambient equilibrium moisture content prior to being encapsulated in the plastic, it would appear that these fibers, when again coming into contact with the environment, would take up moisture and thus swell. This would, of course, lead to a rougher surface.

As shown in the paragraphs above, there are differences in tool wear and surface roughness between different woodfiber plastic products. Differences also exist when these materials are compared to solid wood. Further research is needed to substantiate these findings and to explain the phenomena observed. Also, without a doubt, a better understanding of the necessary process parameters to cut these materials will lead to improved results in respect to tool wear and surface roughness.

Conclusions

This study on tool wear when cutting woodfiber plastic composite materials showed large differences among the five different products tested. Smaller differences in respect to surface roughness after cutting do exist, too.

Tool wear was smallest when cutting the solid wood (white pine) control sample. In this case, the knife's nose width (NW) after cutting 125 feet increased from 9.0 μm to 10.4 μm . ChoiceDek, on the other hand, had a NW 65.6 μm after 125 feet of cutting. The other four materials ranged between 25.0 and 37.0 μm after 125 feet of cutting. Woodfiber plastic composites, according to these preliminary results, wear tools more than does solid wood. However, some of the formulations are more benign than are others. Reasons for these observations could be possible contaminants contained in some of the woodfiber plastic composites and the pigments used for coloring. However, specific analyses of these observations have yet to be conducted.

The surface roughness after cutting the woodfiber plastic composite materials is more similar to solid wood than was the tool wear. In fact, some of the materials tested had a smoother surface after cutting than did the wood control sample (white pine). Others, especially the ones that wore the knife heavily, had slightly rougher surfaces than the control sample. Potentially, the moisture uptake of the woodfiber in the composite materials could lead to a rougher surface after cutting due to swelling. However, no investigation into this theory was conducted.

OVERALL DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

This preliminary study into the material properties of woodfiber plastic composites when exposed to secondary manufacturing processes exposed differences between solid wood and the composite materials. Surface roughness after sanding was similar for all specimens including the wood control sample, the material removal rate (MRR) and the sanding belt life were very different. Tool wear after cutting 125 feet was drastically different among the products tested. None of the composite materials wore the knife as little as did the solid wood control sample. One of the woodfiber plastic composites did wear the knife almost twice as much as did the other samples. Surface roughness after cutting varied somewhat, too. This is not surprising when the wear of the knives is so different as we observed.

Further research efforts into the phenomena observed in this study are necessary. First, the findings made have to be substantiated with more repetitions. Then, hypotheses for specific observations have to be made and tested.

Only by gaining a better understanding of these new materials and their respective behavior when subjected to secondary manufacturing processes can these products be made a competitive alternative for various applications. There is no question that woodfiber plastic composite offers a viable alternative for various applications in the area of secondary forest products. The research efforts at North Carolina State University will help industry to overcome the obstacles in implementing these materials and open new, more competitive alternatives for a wide variety of products.

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FIGURES AND TABLES

Figure 1. -- Belt sander with specimen and weight.

Figure 2. – MRR (lb/min) for various specimens against time. The trendlines are calculated using least square regression.

Figure 3. – Tool wear measurements – measuring the nose width (NW) after each test cycle

Figure 4. – Routertable, single insert tool holder, specimen fixture and test specimen.

Figure 5. – NW of knife used to cut ChoiceDek woodfiber plastic composite after 0, 31, 63, 94, and 125 feet cut at five different positions along the cutting edge.

Figure 6. – Blade used to cut the ChoiceDek material prior to cutting.

Figure 7. – Blade used to cut the ChoiceDek material after 125 feet of cutting.

Figure 8. – Blade used to cut the white pine material after 125 feet of cutting.

Figure 9. –Damaged knife-edge from cutting the ChoiceDek material due to a local impurity in the material.

TABLE 1. – Experimental design for sanding tests.

Material	Pressure (psi)	Abrasive	Grit
CHOICEDEK	0.50	Al ₂ O ₃	100
FIBERON	0.50	Al ₂ O ₃	100
SMARTDECK	0.50	Al ₂ O ₃	100
TREX	0.50	Al ₂ O ₃	100
MAPLE	0.50	Al ₂ O ₃	100

TABLE 2. – Results from the sanding tests.

Material	MRR Average (lb/min)	MRR Max. (lb/min)	MRR Std. Dev. (lb/min)	Roughness (µin)	Belt Life (min)
CHOICEDEK	0.012	0.030	0.0065	526	40
FIBERON	0.010	0.018	0.0031	531	150
SMARTDECK	0.005	0.014	0.0033	508	40
TREX	0.006	0.015	0.0033	529	31
MAPLE	0.006	0.010	0.0020	503	54

TABLE 3. – Test set-up at the router for the tool-wear measurements.

Parameter	Setting
Spindle speed	18,000 rpm
Feed Speed	350 ipm
Depth of cut	1/16 inches/pass
Blade carbide grade	Sandvik H3F
Length of cut	23.5 inches/pass
Cuts per test	16
Number of tests	4
Mode of cut	Conventional

TABLE 4. – NW for all six materials tested at 0, 31.3, 62.7, 94, and 125 feet cutting length.

Material	NW (μ m) after				
	0 feet	31.3 feet	62.7 feet	94.0 feet	125.0 feet
CHOICEDEK	7.0	40.0	53.0	57.0	65.6
EXCEL	9.0	18.3	20.3	23.4	31.5
FIBERON	5.0	10.0	18.0	22.0	25.0
SMARTDECK	7.0	14.6	21.4	27.4	37.0
TREX	8.0	15.4	20.0	22.0	25.4
WHITE PINE	9.0	10.0	10.0	10.4	10.4

TABLE 5. – Surface roughness perpendicular and lengthwise to the cut for all six materials tested.

Material	Roughness	Roughness border	Roughness center
	perpendicular	lengthwise	
	Rq (μ in)	Rq (μ in)	
CHOICEDEK	276	222	167
EXCEL	NA	112	NA
FIBERON	116	69	71
SMARTDECK	249	200	211
TREX	244	152	152
MAPLE	180	208	244